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Interactions of Eutectic Fe-Si-B Alloy with Graphite Crucibles

TMT4500 - Materials Technology, Specialization Project

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Preface

This study investigates the interactions between eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles around the melting point of the alloy. The study is a part of the EU-project AMADEUS, which is investigating new phase change materials for latent heat thermal energy storage systems. Fe-Si-B alloy is found to be a promising candidate for this application.

This study is the basis for evaluation for the course TMT4500 Materials Technology, Specialization Project at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim.

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Abstract

This study is a part of the EU-project AMADEUS, which is investigating new materials for latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES). The main objective is to investigate interactions between eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles, to see if they are possible candidates for LHTES systems. Earlier studies of Fe-Si-B alloy with graphite crucibles were conducted by Bettina Grorud in her master thesis (Grorud 2018) [1]. Grorud's results were promising, so this study will continue working with the same materials.

This project had two intermediate objectives. The first to simulate a LHTES with temperature cycles around the Fe-Si-B alloy's melting point. The second was to investigate why the alloy does not melt at the theoretical melting point, as previous studies have reported trouble with melting the same alloy. Heating experiments were also conducted in this study, to investigate the real melting temperature.

In all the samples from the experiments that simulated a LHTES, with multiple temperature cycles around the theoretical melting temperature 1157°C melted. Not all of the heating experiments melted, even 100°C above the theoretical melting point. Chemical analyses were therefore conducted to find out why. In the experiments that did not melt, the chemical analyses showed boron particles with 5 at% carbon on the surface of the alloy in the sample, which is the phase $B_{4+\delta}C$. $B_{4+\delta}C$ has a melting temperature of approximately 2127°C[2]. The maximum temperature used in the experiments was 1550 °C, hence $B_{4+\delta}C$ would be solid. As this phase was found on the surface of the alloy, it could have create a shell around the alloy and prevented the alloy from melting. Another possible reason to why the alloy is not always melting, could be that the master alloy's composition deviates from the eutectic composition. The chemical composition of the master alloy made in this study deviates somewhat from the eutectic composition, due to impurities. This would affect the melting temperature of

the alloy.

SiC particles were found in all analyzed samples on the bottom of the alloy, where it is in contact with the graphite crucible, and on the top of the alloy. Silicon carbide has a melting point of 2830°C[3]. From the pictures taken of the samples during the analyses, SiC can be observed agglomerating around the top and bottom of the alloy in the samples. This could indicate that SiC is creating a protective shell around the alloy, which does not melt at the temperatures used in the experiments, due to its high melting point. However, silicon carbide has a high thermal conductivity, k , in the range of 0,5-1,2 W/cm*K [4]. Which is in the same range as Fe-Si-B alloy at 27°C; 0,852 W/cm*K [1]. A high thermal conductivity means that the thermal gradient within the SiC particles is low, and the heat can move on to the Fe-Si-B alloy. This could indicate that the unwanted silicon carbide particles are not an obstacle for this system's application as LHTES.

Sammendrag

Denne studien er en del av EU-prosjektet AMADEUS, som undersøker nye materialer for lagring av latent termisk energi (Latent Heat Thermal Energy storage, LHTES). Hovedmålet med denne studien er å undersøke interaksjonene mellom eutektisk Fe-Si-B-legering og grafittdigler, for å se om denne legeringen er en mulig kandidat til LHTES. Tidligere studier av Fe-Si-B-legering med grafittdigler ble utført av Bettina Grorud i hennes masteroppgave (Grorud 2018) [1]. Groruds resultater var lovende, derfor vil denne studien fortsette arbeidet med de samme materialene.

Denne studien hadde to delmål. Det første var å simulere en LHTES med rundt Fe-Si-B legerings smeltepunkt. Det andre var å undersøke hvorfor legeringen ikke smelter ved teoretisk smeltepunkt, da tidligere studier har rapportert problemer med smelting av samme legering. Oppvarmingsforsøk ble også utført i denne studien for å undersøke den virkelige smeltetemperaturen.

Alle prøvene i eksperimentene som simulerte en LHTES, med flere rundt den teoretiske smeltetemperaturen 1157°C smeltet. Ikke alle smeltet, selv 100°C over det teoretiske smeltepunktet. Kjemiske analyser ble derfor gjennomført for å undersøke hvorfor legeringen ikke smeltet. I forsøkene som ikke smeltet, viste de kjemiske analysene borpartikler med 5 at% karbon på overflaten av legeringen i prøven, som mest sannsynlig er fasen $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$. $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ har en smeltetemperatur på omtrent 2127°C [2]. Maksimumstemperaturen som ble brukt i forsøkene var 1550°C , og derfor ville $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ være i fast fase. Da denne fasen ble funnet på

overflaten på legeringen, kan den ha skapt et skall rundt legeringen og forhindret legeringen i å smelte. En annen mulig forklaring til hvorfor legeringen ikke alltid smelter, er at masterlegeringens sammensetning avviker noe fra den eutektiske sammensetningen pga urenheter. Dette ville påvirke smeltetemperaturen til legeringen.

SiC-partikler ble funnet i alle de analyserte prøvene på bunnen av legeringen, der den er i kontakt med grafittdigelen og på toppen av legeringen. Silisiumkarbid har et smeltepunkt på 2830 °C [3]. Fra analysebildene, kan SiC observeres å ha agglomerert rundt toppen og bunnen av legeringen i prøvene. Dette kan tyde på at SiC skaper et beskyttende skall rundt legeringen, som ikke smelter ved temperaturene som brukes i forsøkene, på grunn av dets høye smeltepunkt. Imidlertid har silisiumkarbid en høy termisk ledningsevne, k , i området 0,5-1,2 W/cm*K [4]. Som ligger i samme område som Fe-Si-B legering ved 27 °C; 0,85 2W/cm*K [1]. En høy termisk ledningsevne betyr at temperatur gradienten i SiC partiklene er lav, og varmen enkelt kan nå frem til Fe-Si-B legering i midten. Dette kan tyde på at de uønskede silisiumkarbidpartiklene ikke er et hinder for dette systemets applikasjon som LHTES.

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1. Introduction

EU-project AMADEUS is investigating new materials for latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES). These materials are phase change materials (PCM), with latent heat in the range 2-4 MJ/kg in the phase transition. The material is heated to ultra high temperatures up to 2000°C with energy sources such as solar, electrical and waste heat[5].

The energy is stored as ultra high temperature latent heat storage in the molten metal phase, which is covered by an advanced thermal insulation and PCM casing. As the molten metal is allowed to cool down to solid state, the latent heat is released to the surroundings. The system is thermally insulated by a casing which absorb the latent heat and convert it into electrical energy by using photovoltaic and thermionic effects. This will be tried out using a new form of solid-state device, a hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) device.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the Amadeus project [5]. The concept of the Amadeus project is that the phase change material will utilize the input energy that is e.g. solar, electric or waste heat from the industry, as illustrated in green on the left. The energy will be stored as latent thermal heat in the phase change material. The material will melt and in the molten state, it can store the energy until it is needed. The energy storage system with the phase change material and the vessel can be seen in orange in the centre of the figure. When the material solidifies, it releases the latent thermal heat as energy to its surroundings. An emitter will receive the energy and with a collector and PV (photovoltaic) cell, the energy will be converted into electricity. This conversion is illustrated in blue at the right in the figure.

Silicon has shown to be a very interesting material for LHTES-systems, due to its high enthalpy of fusion. However, there is a challenge connected to using silicon as a material for LHTES-systems, since silicon expands upon solidification. It is preferable that the system has the same volume as liquid as a solid, as the material will be melted and solidified multiple times in cycles. An expansion upon solidification could cause cracks in the casing, which would reduce its lifetime.

1.1 Thermal energy storage systems

Thermal energy storage systems are utilized in energy production, where the energy production exceeds the energy demand. An example is the solar energy production, where there is a time gap between when the energy is produced and when it is needed. To solve this problem, thermal energy storage systems are used for storage for a certain time. [6]

Thermal energy storage systems often utilize phase change materials to store the energy, due to their ability to store up to 5-14 times more heat per volume unit than more common heat storage materials such as water, masonry or rock. [7]

1.2 Phase change materials

A Phase Change Material (PCM) is a material that can store and release large amounts of energy, often in the form of heat. The change in phase can be between all combinations of the three phases; liquid, solid and gas. The phase change between liquid and solid is commercially the most promising. During the phase change from solid to liquid the material absorb the energy as latent heat with a constant temperature, and when the phase changes from liquid to solid the material releases the energy to its surroundings. [8]

Figure 1.2: Principle of Phase Change Materials

A PCM should possess certain thermodynamic properties in order to be classified as a PCM. A high latent heat of fusion per unit volume is required to store as much energy in the material as possible. The material should possess a high thermal conductivity in order to have as small temperature gradients as possible, to charge and discharge the energy effectively from the PCM. A small volume change in the phase transformation is needed to run cycles of charging and discharging the PCM, without introduction cracks and then possibly breakage of the unit containing the PCM. Chemical stability is another property desired from a PCM, in order to keep the material from reacting with the casing material. High nucleation rate in the liquid state is wanted, in order to avoid super cooling. In addition, the material should melt congruently, which means that the

material should keep stoichiometric composition in the liquid and solid phase [9].

1.3 Objectives

This study is a continuation of the work done by Bettina Grorud on her master thesis (Grorud 2018) [1] and Caroline Sindland (Sindland 2018) on her summer project [10]. They were studying the possibility of using different Si-B alloys with graphite crucibles as a LTHES. Their work concluded with that eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy has the most promising properties. The most significant results were that the Fe-Si-B alloy has almost no volume difference between liquid and solid state ($dV = -0.01 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) [1], which is an important criterion as the alloy is stored in a casing made of graphite. Another important result was that silicon had a lower activity in Fe-Si-B alloy than in the other Si-B alloys that were investigated. Low activity of silicon means that silicon will be less reactive with carbon from the graphite crucible, as silicon has a high affinity to carbon and silicon carbide is a stable compound at room temperature. Formation of silicon carbide is highly unwanted for this application, as it will degrade the graphite crucible and change the properties of the system. The goal is to have as little interactions as possible between the alloy and the crucible material.

Graphite crucibles have properties that make them a favorable candidate as casing material for LTHES. The graphite used in the crucibles has a high thermal conductivity ($140 \text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$) [11] and low thermal expansion ($4.8\cdot 10^{-6}/\text{K}$) [11]. These properties will prevent thermal shock and provide an even heat distribution in the crucibles during the high temperature experiments.

This study has two main objectives:

1. To investigate the interactions between Fe-Si-B alloy and the graphite crucible, by simulating a LTHES over 5 days.

2. To investigate the real melting point of alloy, as previous studies show that the alloy sometimes does not melt above the theoretical melting point of 1157°C.

In addition to these two main objectives, it is important to investigate the microstructure of the alloy, to see if the wanted composition is obtained after the experiments. This is the eutectic composition with 64.2 wt% Fe, 26.4 wt% Si and 9.4 wt% B, and the goal is that alloy has constant composition during the temperature cycles. Eutectic solution will provide the sharpest transition between the solid and liquid state in the alloy, with the smallest temperature interval between the two states. A small temperature interval between solid and liquid state is wanted, as a large temperature interval could introduce thermal stress to the system, and it would take more time to charge and discharge the energy in the system.

2. Theory

This section will give an overview why Fe-Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles are chosen as materials in high temperature latent heat storage systems.

2.1 Fe-Si-B alloy as a phase change material

Fe-Si-B alloy has shown promising properties as a phase change material. Some of the most important values for a phase change material are listed for pure silicon and Fe-Si-B alloy in table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Characteristic properties for Si and Fe-Si-B alloy. Calculated by Grorud, 2018. [1]

Composition	Si	$Fe_{0.64}Si_{0.27}B_{0.09}$
dV [cm^3/cm^3]	0,11	-0,01
dH_{fus}^{ideal} [kJ/cm^3]	4,09	4,50
dH_{fus}^{real} [kJ/cm^3]	4,09	3,67
k at 27°C [$\text{W}/\text{cm}^*\text{K}$]	1,422	0,852
k at 1127°C [$\text{W}/\text{cm}^*\text{K}$]	0,287	0,326
Calculated T_m [°C]	1412	1157

Silicon was considered a good candidate for phase change materials due to its high enthalpy of fusion of $4,09 \text{ kJ}/\text{cm}^3$. However, silicon expands during solidification, which could introduce cracks to the container material. Hence, iron and boron were added to create an alloy with almost no volume expansion upon solidification. The real enthalpy of fusion for $Fe_{0.64}Si_{0.27}B_{0.09}$ is somewhat lower than for pure silicon.

2.2 Graphite crucibles

Graphite crucibles consists of carbon in the form of graphite. Graphite is a naturally occurring crystalline structure of carbon. The carbon is structured in a hexagonal pattern in thin sheets with thickness of one carbon atom. Each carbon atom in the hexagonal pattern is joined to three other carbon atoms through a covalent bonding. The fourth electron of carbon is therefore free to move around within the structure, which makes graphite electrical conductive. The layers in graphite are connected through weak van der Waals forces, and the layers are therefore easily separated. This is gives graphite a low hardness compared to other materials.[12]

When producing the carbon crucibles, the graphite material is cold isostatic pressed together. This means the graphite has the same properties in all directions. Isostatic graphite has a low thermal expansion ($4.8 \cdot 10^{-6}/K$), and high thermal conductivity ($140 \text{ W}/(\text{m} \cdot K)$) [11]. These are important properties that will prevent thermal shock and provide an even heat distribution in the carbon crucibles during high temperature experiments. A high thermal conductivity is also preferred, as the casing material of the LHTES are thought to transport the latent heat of the alloy out from the system through the casing .

2.3 Wetting

Wetting is a liquid's ability to spread out when it comes in contact with a solid surface. The degree of wetting is determined by the force balance between the adhesive and cohesive forces in the liquid when it is in contact with a surface.

The degree of wetting can be determined by the contact angle between the liquid and the solid, as illustrated in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Contact angle between a liquid and a solid surface[13].

The contact angle can be obtained from Young's equation:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{\gamma_{SG} - \gamma_{SL}}{\gamma_{LG}} \quad (2.1)$$

Where γ_{SG} , γ_{SL} and γ_{LG} denotes the surface tension between the solid phase and the gas phase, the surface tension between the solid phase and liquid phase and the surface tension between the liquid phase and the gas phase, respectively. [14]

When $\theta > 90^\circ$, the wettability is defined as low, and when $\theta < 90^\circ$, the wettability is defined as high. A high wettability between the liquid and the solid is indicating that more of the surface area of the two substances are in contact, and could potentially interact more than two substances with low wettability.

The wetting between the Fe-Si-B alloy and the graphite material in the crucibles, will be discussed further in section 4.1. In this application of Fe-Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles, it is wanted that the alloy has a low wettability on graphite in order to avoid interactions.

Li and Hausner (1995) [15] investigated the melting process of silicon and its

spreading on graphite substrate. In their experiments commercially available graphite material was used as substrate and particles of high purity silicon (99.999%) to be melted in high purity argon (99.998%) atmosphere. They made a schematic representation of the melting process of silicon on graphite, which is shown in figure 2.2. They showed that the silicon had reached total melting when the particles had obtained a half-spherical shape, as can be seen in subfigure (d) in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of the melting process of silicon and its spreading on graphite substrate. (a) before melting, (b) start of melting, (c) during melting, (d) complete melting, (e) during spreading and (f) stabilization. [15]

2.4 The Fe-Si-B-C system and its subsystems

2.4.1 The Fe-Si-B ternary system

The ternary phase diagram for Fe-Si-B alloy is presented in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: The ternary phase diagram for Fe-Si-B alloy, the eutectic point is marked with a yellow star. Calculated by Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) using FactSage (FT Lite database).

At the yellow star in figure 2.3, the eutectic reaction occurs at 1157 °C, according to FactSage. The eutectic composition is 26.4 wt% Si, 64.2 wt% Fe and 9.4 wt% B, and the eutectic reaction is shown in equation 2.2.

At the eutectic point, the liquid solidifies into three different solid phases, that are surrounding the eutectic point in figure 2.3. The expected amount of each phase is found by construction of the Alkamade lines, that are drawn in the phase diagram as shown in figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: The ternary phase diagram for Fe-Si-B alloy, the eutectic point is marked with a red dot, and the Alkemade lines are marked as red lines. Calculated by Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) using FactSage (FT Lite database).

The Alkemade lines are used to create the eutectic phase diagram as illustrated in figure 2.5

Figure 2.5: The eutectic phase diagram for Fe-Si-B at 1157 °C. Calculated by Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) using FactSage (FT Lite database).

Using the Lever rule in the eutectic phase diagram shown in figure 2.5, the phase composition in eutectic solution is as shown in equation 2.3.

$$liq = 68,13 wt\% FeSi(s) + 24,31 wt\% FeB(s) + 7,78 wt\% SiB_6(s) \quad (2.3)$$

2.4.2 Carbon saturated Fe-Si-B alloy

The Fe-Si-B is in direct contact with carbon in the graphite crucible, so it is assumed that the system will become carbon saturated after some time. This is

illustrated in the phase diagram in figure 2.6, which show what phases are precipitated during cooling of the alloy from 1500 to 1000 °C.

Figure 2.6: The phase diagram of carbon saturated Fe-Si-B alloy. The liquidus is estimated to be between 1150 and 1200 °C. Calculated by Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) using FactSage (FT Lite database).

The diagram in figure 2.6 is showing that the phases FeSi, FeB and SiB₆ are precipitating below 1157 °C as predicted from the ternary diagram in figure 2.3. Additionally in the carbon saturated system, the phase B₄C is precipitated at temperatures above 1450 °C.

Table 2.2: Calculated carbon saturation for the Fe_{0.642}Si_{0.264}B_{0.94}B alloy at various temperatures. Calculated by Senior Research Scientist Kai Tang (SINTEF) [16].

T[°C]	Si [wt%]	Fe [wt%]	B [wt%]	C [wt%]	Phase
1400	26.41	64.17	9.38	0.03	B ₄ C
1500	26.39	64.11	9.37	0.13	B ₄ C
1600	26.34	63.98	9.35	0.33	SiC
1700	26.27	63.82	9.33	0.59	SiC

2.4.3 The Fe-Si binary system

The Fe-Si phase diagram is illustrated in figure 2.7, and shows the different phases with varying iron and silicon composition. As seen in the Fe-Si-B ternary phase diagram, the phase FeSi is an eutectic phase. FeSi can be found in the binary phase diagram, with 50 at% Fe and 50 at% Si, and it melts congruently at around 1420 °C.

Figure 2.7: The Fe-Si binary phase diagram. The figure is taken from Kubaschewski (1982)[17].

2.4.4 The Fe-B binary system

The Fe-B phase diagram is presented in figure 2.8. A characteristic of the binary system is the low mutual solubility of the two elements in the solid state. The phase FeB is an eutectic phase in the ternary diagram for Fe-Si-B alloy, and can be found in the Fe-B phase diagram at 50 at% Fe and 50 at% B. FeB melts congruently at 1650 °C.

Figure 2.8: The Fe-B binary phase diagram. The figure is taken from Massalski (1996). [18].

2.4.5 The Si-B binary system

The Si-B phase diagram is presented in figure 2.9. The phase SiB_6 is one of the three eutectic phases in the Fe-Si-B phase diagram, and can be found around 86 %at B in the Si-B phase diagram. This phase melts peritectically at 1850 °C. The more boron rich phase SiB_n can be found on the very right side in the diagram, where $n = 14, 15, 40$, etc. [19].

Figure 2.9: The Si-B binary phase diagram. The figure is taken from Olesinski and Abbaschian (1984). [19].

2.4.6 The Si-C binary system

The binary phase diagram for silicon and carbon is presented in figure 2.10. In the Si-C binary system the only stable compounds are silicon, graphite and silicon carbide. Pure silicon melts at 1408 °C according to the diagram. Due to the

very high melting point of SiC, it is difficult to determine the exact temperatures in the phase diagram. Hence, multiple liquidus lines are suggested.

Figure 2.10: The Si-C binary phase diagram. The figure is taken from Hoel (1995).[20]

Figure 2.11 shows a magnified part of the low carbon part in the Si-C binary phase diagram. Here it is illustrated that silicon only solve very small amounts of carbon, and that carbon content greater than 5 ppm mass of silicon will result in the formation of silicon carbide.

Figure 2.11: The Si-C binary phase diagram, for low carbon content. Calculated by Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) using FactSage (FSupsi database).

2.4.7 The B-C binary system

The B-C binary phase diagram is presented in figure 2.12. According to the diagram in figure 2.6, the phase B_4C will be precipitated at temperatures above 1450 °C in a carbon saturated Fe-Si-B system. B_4C melts congruently at 2458 °C.

Figure 2.12: The B-C binary phase diagram. The figure is taken from Landolt-Börnstein [2].

3. Experimental

The aim of the experimental work in this project is to investigate the interactions between the graphite crucible and the Fe-Si-B alloy. This was done by simulating a LHTES system over 5 days. Two experiments were conducted to investigate the real melting temperature of the alloy. In this section, the raw materials, equipment, procedures for all the experiments are presented. This includes also the production of the master alloy.

3.1 Raw materials

The master alloy is made from the same raw materials as Bettina Grorud (Grorud 2018) and Caroline Sindland (Sindland 2018) used to make their master alloys. Electronic-Grade Silicon (99,9999999998 % Si) from REC Silicon came in granular form. Boron powder used had a purity of 99,9 % and was provided by ZhongNuo Advanced Material Technology Co., Ltd.. Iron was provided in powder form with a purity of 99 % and came from Alfa Aesar.

3.2 Apparatus

The equipment used to conduct the experiments are presented here.

3.2.1 Crucibles

The graphite crucibles used in these experiments were made from cold isostatic pressed graphite with homogeneous properties. In experiments 1-4, crucibles with inner diameter = 1.5 cm, outer diameter = 3 cm and height = 3.4 cm were used. For experiment 5, a crucible with inner diameter = 1.45 cm, outer diameter = 2.1 cm and height = 3.4 cm was used. The crucibles were provided by Toyo Tanso Co., Ltd [21], with quality type IG-15.

Table 3.1: Porosity data for crucibles IG15 provided by Toyo Tanso Co., Ltd [21]

	Bulk Density	Cumulative Pore Volume	Open Porosity	Radius of Average Open Porosity
IG-15	1.90 Mg/m ³	0.052 m ³ /g	10 %	1.4 μm

3.2.2 Graphite tube furnace

The experiments were performed in a vertical graphite tube furnace, which is illustrated in figure 3.1. The heat is supplied by resistive heating, where an electric current through the graphite produces heat. C-type thermocouple is used to measure the temperature inside the furnace, and can be seen in figure 3.1 as the thermocouple is inserted from the top. The tip of the thermocouple is in contact with the lid of a graphite holder, which contains the carbon crucible with alloy inside. The temperature measured, is the temperature on the lid. The distance between the lid and the bottom of the crucible inside is 50 mm. The temperature gradient between these two positions was measured at around 1500°C, since the experiments were conducted around this temperature. The measurements showed that the lid of the holder was 19,5°C higher than the bottom of the crucible where the alloy was located during experiments, which is illustrated in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.1: Figure of the tube furnace used in experiments. Made by Jakobsson [22].

Figure 3.2: Measured temperature gradient between the thermocouple tip position during experiments and the bottom of the crucible holder where the alloy is located in the graphite tube furnace. At measurements around 1500°C, a temperature gradient of 19,5°C was measured.

3.2.3 Cutting and mounting

After the experiments, the crucibles were cooled down and cut. First horizontally, in order to remove the graphite material which was not in contact with the alloy. Then the crucibles were cut in half in vertical direction, through the alloy. This was done in order to investigate the microstructure of the alloy and the interactions between the alloy and the graphite crucible.

Samples 1, 2, 4 and 5 were mounted with epoxy, using ClaroCit EpoFix cold-setting embedding resin.

Figure 3.3: Half of the crucible from experiment 4 mounted in epoxy.

Sample 3 was mounted in ClaroCit EpoFix cold-setting embedding resin together with Idoform.

Figure 3.4: The particle on the right is the alloy from experiment 3, which did not melt. It has the same shape as before the heat treatment, however had a different surface color than before the experiment. Even if the alloy did not melt, the color difference at the surface indicates that a reaction took place and could explain why the alloy did not melt. Therefore, one heat treated particle from the experiment was mounted together with a particle of master alloy (for reference), which is on the left in the sample.

3.2.4 Grinding and polishing

After the cutting and mounting of the samples, they had to be grinded and polished as a preparation for microscopical analyses. All the samples were washed thoroughly with soap, water and ethanol between each step of the grinding and polishing.

3.2.4.1 Sample 1, 2, 4 and 5

Step 1 Piatto 220 was used together with water, the speed was set to 150 rpm and the sample was grinded for about 5 minutes.

Step 2 $9\mu\text{m}$ Largo was used together with spray containing $9\mu\text{m}$ diamond particles on the sheet. The speed was 150 rpm and the sample was polished for 5 minutes. To avoid friction between the sample and the sheet, lubricant was

added.

Step 3 3 μm Aksal Mol was used together with spray containing 3 μm diamond particles on the sheet, and lubricant. The sample was polished for 5 minutes and the speed was 150 rpm.

Step 4 1 μm MD Nap together with spray containing 1 μm diamond particles and lubricant. Speed was 150 rpm.

3.2.4.2 Sample 3

To polish sample 3, a different program was used for grinding and polishing. This was done because of suspicion of a carbide layer on the surface of the particles, and carbides require a different grinding and polishing routine than metals. This routine was designed by Sethulakshmy Jayakumari (NTNU).

Step 1 Piano 120 sheet was used for 5 minutes together with water, the speed was set at 150 rpm.

Step 2 Piano 220 sheet was used for 5 minutes together with water, the speed was set at 150 rpm.

Step 3 Dac 6 μm sheet was used for 3 minutes together with a liquid containing diamond particles of size 6 μm , the speed was set at 150 rpm

Step 4 Piano 1200 sheet was used for 5 minutes together with water, the speed was set at 150 rpm.

Step 5 Allegro 9 μm sheet was used for 3 minutes together with a liquid containing diamond particles of size 9 μm , and the speed was set at 150 rpm.

Step 6 Dac 6 μm sheet was used for 3 minutes together with a liquid containing diamond particles of size 6 μm , the speed was set at 150 rpm.

Step 7 Nap-B 1 μm sheet was used for 3 minutes together with a liquid containing diamond particles of size 1 μm , the speed was set at 150 rpm.

3.2.5 Characterization

To investigate the microstructure of the alloy and the interactions between the graphite crucible and the alloy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used. To do a semi-quantitative analysis identifying the elements present in the samples, Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) was used. All elements with atomic number higher than 11 can be detected by EDS, however the EDS used in this study was equipped with a detector which could to some degree detect boron ($Z = 5$). Hence, the analysis the phases containing boron might not be accurate. Samples 3, 4 and 5 were investigated using LVFESEM Zeiss Supra 55 VP which is located at NTNU, Trondheim.

To do further investigation of the microstructure and interactions, an analysis with Electron Probe Microanalysis was conducted of samples 2, 3, 4 and 5. The analysis was performed by Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes (NTNU) using the JXA-8500F Field Emission Electron Probe Microanalyzer located at NTNU, Trondheim.

3.3 Preparation of the master alloy

The master alloy had to be made before running cycle experiments in the tube furnace.

In experiment 1 and 2, master alloy made by Caroline Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10] was used. This alloy has the sample-ID SFB-BA1 [10]. There was enough master alloy from Sindland to run two experiments, but for the rest of the experiments in this project, more master alloy had to be made and an induction furnace was used. 300 g of master alloy was made, amounts of the raw materials are given in table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Weighing of master alloy

Element	wt%	grams
Si	26,4	79,2
Fe	64,2	192,6
B	9,4	28,2
total	100	300

The raw materials were placed in layers in the crucible according to their melting point. The element with highest melting point was placed at the bottom, followed by the element with the middle melting point and on the very top the element with lowest melting point. The melting point for pure boron, iron and silicon is 2026,85 °C, 1535,85 °C and 1411,85 °C respectively, according to HSC Chemistry 9 [3]. Boron was placed at the bottom, then iron and at the top silicon. The idea was that the pure silicon would melt first and the liquid would run down to the other layers and speed up the melting process.

For production of the alloy an alumina crucible was chosen as the inner crucible. The outer crucible was made of carbon, and was of standard size which fitted the crucible holder inside the induction furnace. A type C thermocouple was placed in between the crucibles to measure the temperature, which will not be the same as the temperature inside the crucible where the alloy is produced. However, in order to make the casting process inside the furnace easier and not to contaminate the alloy, the thermocouple was placed in between the crucibles.

The atmosphere during operation was 5N Ar at 1 atm, and the furnace was flushed with argon gas twice. The alloy was heated up to 1700°C and this temperature was held for 1 hour. The heating speed was approximately 1°C/sec.

During the holding time, the silicon pellets were observed to be melting from the window on top of the furnace. After 1 hour of holding the temperature at 1700°C, the alloy was observed to have completely melted. Then the alloy was casted inside the furnace into a copper mould with water cooling. During the

casting, the crucible accidentally fell into the mould and the casted alloy. This was not suppose to happen, but the alloy is believed to have solidified or partially solidified due to the copper mould with water cooling which ensures a fast solidification of casted material in the furnace. Unfortunately, the crucible holder has no mechanism to fix the crucible when casting.

After the master alloy was casted, it was crushed into pieces with size of approximately 2-3 cm.

3.3.1 ICP-MS

The ICP-MS analysis of the master alloy made by the author is presented in table 3.3. This was the alloy used in experiments 3, 4 and 5.

Table 3.3: ICP-MS analysis of master alloy made by the author.

	wt% Si	wt% Fe	wt% B	wt% Al	wt% Mn	wt% Cr
Eutectic composition	26.46	64.16	9.38	-	-	-
Results	25.65	63.33	8.47	0.68	0.23	0.02
RSD [%]	1.6	2.9	2.3	5.0	3.4	2.3
Normalized results	26.07	64.37	8.61	0.69	0.23	0.02

The ICP-MS analysis done by Caroline Sindland of the alloy with sample-ID SFB-BA1 [10] can be found in table 3.4. This was the alloy used in experiments 1 and 2 in this project.

Table 3.4: ICP-MS analysis of master alloy made by Caroline Sindland (Sindland 2018) with sample-ID SFB-BA1 [10].

	wt% Si	wt% Fe	wt% B	wt% Al	wt% Mn	wt% Cr	wt% S
Eutectic composition	26.46	64.16	9.38	-	-	-	-
Results	27	56	8.1	0.069	0.21	0.020	0.018

3.3.2 XRD

As mentioned in section 2.4.1, it is expected to find the phases FeSi, FeB and SiB₆ in the master alloy. In the results from XRD analysis shown in figure 3.5, the

phases FeSi and FeB were identified. SiB₆ was not found. Silicon rich phases with small amounts of boron are also identified, but it is uncertain how accurate these results are as these phases are not expected to be found at the eutectic point in the phase diagram. The phase Fe₂B was also found, which is not expected to be found in the eutectic composition. However, according to the phase diagram in figure 2.8 a mixture of the phases Fe₂B and FeB can be found next to the FeB phase boundary line. If there is more Fe than B present in this phase, it would be expected to find Fe₂B.

(Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Figure 3.5: Results of XRD analysis of the master alloy made by the author.

3.4 Wettability furnace

Experiments in a wettability furnace were done to investigate the real melting temperature of the master alloy. The wettability angle was also investigated to determine if the alloy wetted the substrate or not, hence this could indicate if the alloy interacts with the substrate material. The experiments in this project

used graphite as the crucible material, so graphite was chosen as a substrate. Alumina was chosen to see if there was any significant difference in melting temperature of the alloy and wettability angle.

Two experiments in the wettability furnace were conducted. The master alloy was crushed to fine powder and then pressed into a small particle that could fit into the 10 mm sample holder. The small alloy particles were placed on graphite and alumina substrate, respectively. The furnace was flushed and inserted with 5N Ar atmosphere to 1 atm pressure. Then the particles were heated inside the furnace with heating rate of 5°C/min until complete melting. Thermocouple type C was used to measure the temperature inside the furnace. A camera took pictures of the sample every second, and when the particle obtained a spherical shape it was believed to have completely melted according to figure 2.2.

Figure 3.6: Illustration of the wettability furnace used in the wettability experiments [23].

3.5 Experiments

Here, an overview of the 5 experiments that were conducted in this study is presented. All of the experiments were conducted in the tube furnace described in section 3.2.2, and all of the crucibles are of type IG15 as described in section

3.2.1. In experiment 5, a crucible with thinner walls was used, however it was of the same quality type IG15 as the other 4 crucibles. In experiment 1 and 2, the master alloy used was made by Caroline Sindland (Sindland 2018) and had sample-ID SFB-BA1 [10], and the master alloy used in experiment 3, 4 and 5 was made by the author.

The samples of master alloy was weight out to be $6.05 \pm 0.026\text{g}$. The crucibles in experiments 1-4 weighted $35.47 \pm 0.076\text{g}$ and in experiment 5 the crucible weight 14.48 g . The weight loss during the experiments was $0.01 \pm 0.005\text{g}$.

Table 3.5: Overview of the experiments conducted in this project. Experiment 1 and 3 was done to investigate the real melting point of the alloy. Experiment 2, 4 and 5 were experiments done to simulate a LHTES over 5 days.

Exp.No.	Program	Purpose	Melted?
1	Heating	Check melting	Yes
2	Temp. cycles	Simulate a LHTES	Yes
3	Heating	Check melting	No
4	Temp. cycles	Simulate a LHTES	Yes
5	Temp. cycles	Simulate a LHTES	Yes

3.5.1 Experiment 1

As mentioned, earlier work on Fe-Si-B alloy done by Grorud (Grorud 2018) and Sindland (Sindland 2018) have reported that the alloy does melt above the theoretical eutectic melting point. Therefore, experiment 1 was conducted to investigate if the alloy melted if the temperature was held at 1550°C for one hour and then one hour at 1300°C . The temperature profile can be seen in figure 3.7. A picture of the crucible after the heat treatment can be found in figure 3.8. The surface of the alloy is relatively smooth, however small spherical particles have appeared on the surface. The particles were fixed to the surface, and when the crucible was cut, the alloy was in one piece. This indicates that the alloy had melted on the inside.

Figure 3.7: The temperature profile for experiment 1 is illustrated in blue. The orange line is the theoretical eutectic melting point of the Fe-Si-B alloy.

Figure 3.8: Experiment 1, graphite crucible with Fe-Si-B alloy after the heat treatment.

3.5.2 Experiment 2

Experiment 1 was considered melted. To be sure that experiment 2 over 5 days would melt, the first hour of the experiment was set to 1550°C for one hour. Then it was exposed to temperatures $T = 1157 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$ with three hours holding time at each temperature. The temperature control on the furnace was at this time manual, and therefore the temperature cycles were conducted only during daytime. During nighttime the temperature was set to 1137°C. The temperature profile in experiment 2 can be found in figure 3.9. A picture of the crucible after the temperature cycles can be found in figure 3.10. The alloy had a completely smooth surface without any particles of defects, and was in one piece when the crucible was cut in half. This indicates that the alloy had melted during the experiment.

Figure 3.9: Temperature cycles done in experiment 2.

Figure 3.10: Experiment 2, graphite crucible with Fe-Si-B alloy after the temperature cycles around the melting point. The alloy is totally smooth on the surface, and is believed to have melted.

3.5.3 Experiment 3

More master alloy had to be made after experiment 2, and experiment 3 was the first experiment with this new master alloy. A heat treatment was done to see if the alloy melted. The temperature was set to 1250°C for one hour, the temperature profile can be found in figure 3.11. In figure 3.12 it can be seen that the alloy has not melted at all, and the same shaped particles from the master alloy are still intact. However, the particles no longer have a metallic surface and this indicates that the alloy has reacted in some degree.

Figure 3.11: Temperature profile for experiment 3 is illustrated in blue. The orange line is the theoretical eutectic melting temperature.

Figure 3.12: Experiment 3, graphite crucible with Fe-Si-B alloy after the heat treatment.

3.5.4 Experiment 4

In experiment 4 the temperature varies between 1550°C and 1137°C, with holding time of three hours at each temperature. Total 16 temperature cycles were

conducted and the temperature profile can be seen in figure 3.13. At this point, an automatic control of the tube furnace was installed and used. Hence it was possible to conduct temperature cycles during the night over the 5 days period. In figure 3.14 the crucible with alloy after the experiment is shown. The surface is quite uneven, and the alloy looks like it did not melt. After cutting the alloy was observed to be in one piece, and is believed to have melted on the inside but not of the surface.

Figure 3.13: Temperature cycles done on experiment 4, illustrated by the blue line. The orange line is the theoretical eutectic melting temperature.

Figure 3.14: Experiment 4, graphite crucible with Fe-Si-B alloy after the temperature cycles around the melting point. The surface is quite uneven and is believed to have not melted on the surface.

3.5.5 Experiment 5

The temperature profile conducted in experiment 5 is the same as in experiment 4. However, the alloy appeared to have completely melted as seen in figure 3.16. The surface is completely smooth and no particles or defects can be observed.

Figure 3.15: Temperature cycles done on experiment 5

Figure 3.16: Experiment 5, graphite crucible with Fe-Si-B alloy after the temperature cycles around the melting point.

4. Results

4.1 Wettability experiments

The pictures taken in the wettability experiments are presented in figure 4.1. They are taken at the point of complete melting, according to figure 2.2, when the particles have obtained a circular shape.

Figure 4.1: Results from the wettability experiments with a particle of Fe-Si-B alloy on different substrate. (a) is done on graphite substrate and the contact angle between the graphite and the droplet is 101° . (b) is done on alumina substrate and the contact angle between the alumina substrate and the alloy is 106° .

According to the results in figure 4.1, the contact angles between the two substrates are greater than 90° , which is indicating that the alloy has a low wettability on these materials. However, one experiment on each substrate is not enough to conclude.

4.2 SEM and EDS

SEM pictures and EDS analysis were taken of samples 3, 4 and 5, at different magnifications. The results presented in this section is chosen as a selection of representative pictures for the samples.

4.2.1 Sample 3 - heated to 1250°C, holding time 1 hour

4.2.1.1 Heat treated particle

The microstructure in the middle of the heat treated particle has a lamellar structure, as can be observed in figure 4.2. A lamellar structure could be an indication that the alloy is eutectic in the centre [24]. On the edge in figure 4.2 (b) black particles can be observed, which likely is SiC or B₄C.

Figure 4.2: SEM pictures taken of sample 3. (a) is taken at 4000X magnification at the middle of one of the heat treated particles from sample 3. (b) taken at 1000X magnification of the same particle as in (a). Black particles can be seen along the edge, which most likely are SiC or B₄C.

The EDS analysis of the surface of the heat treated particles, show high levels of carbon, ranging from 8.39 to 73.84 at% carbon in the EDS analysis spots. In table 4.1 the phases B₄C and SiC was identified. In table 4.2 no known phases could be identifies, only high levels of carbon. The oxygen level of the phases on

the surface is around 1-3 at%, with some exceptions that show 9-10 at% oxygen and one spot with 18.55 at% oxygen.

Figure 4.3: EDS analysis nr. 1 of the surface of the heat treated particles from sample 3, showing the spots where the EDS analysis was conducted which is presented in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: EDS analysis no. 1 of one of the heat treated particles from sample 3, as shown in figure4.3.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	12.32	7.31	56.99	2.75	19.96	0.68	B ₄ C
2	39.26	1.17	0.26	9.33	43.28	6.70	SiC
3	10.27	5.82	51.17	3.79	27.88	1.09	B ₄ C
4	13.25	0.16	9.11	10.74	64.21	2.52	Oxides/carbides?
5	8.33	11.94	51.74	4.71	22.38	0.91	Carbides?
6	8.47	3.82	64.49	1.31	21.21	0.71	B ₄ C
7	15.62	7.19	50.79	3.24	21.92	1.24	Carbides?

Figure 4.4: EDS analysis nr. 2 of the surface of the heat treated particles from sample 3. showing the spots where the EDS analysis was conducted which is presented in table 4.2

Table 4.2: EDS analysis no. 2 of one of the heat treated particles from sample 3 as shown in figure 4.4.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]
1	23.83	8.30	42.32	2.54	21.15	1.86
2	15.42	8.85	64.94	1.49	8.39	0.92
3	22.75	9.77	50.73	1.43	14.40	0.92
4	16.33	8.17	52.69	2.10	19.76	0.96
5	2.69	3.41	16.12	2.86	73.84	1.07
6	21.91	0.55	2.66	18.55	49.79	6.54
7	16.05	7.10	38.37	3.58	33.75	1.15

4.2.1.2 Master alloy as reference

SEM and EDS analyses of the master alloy were conducted as a reference to the analyses conducted of the heat treated particle, in order to see if there was any significant differences.

The same eutectic structure as in the heat treated particle can be seen in the

middle of the master alloy. In addition a bigger white phase can be observed across the SEM picture in figure 4.5 (b). This is possibly a primary phase, and is precipitated before the eutectic structure around.

Figure 4.5: SEM pictures taken of the master alloy as reference to the particles taken from sample 3. (a) is taken at 250X magnification and (b) is taken at 1000X magnification.

The analysis in table 4.3 show high levels of oxygen and carbon. The oxygen

level ranges from 5.99 to 11.55 at% and the carbon content varies from 8.74 to 22.93 at%. These are very high levels as the alloy is supposed to contain only the elements Fe, Si and B. Since these levels of impurities were found in the master alloy (which has not been heat treated after production), the contamination of impurities must have happened during production of the master alloy. However, it is uncertain if the whole master alloy possesses the same levels of oxygen and carbon or if this particle was an exception.

Figure 4.6: EDS analysis of a particle of master alloy used as reference from sample 3. The spots are showing where the EDS analysis was conducted, and the results are presented in table 4.3

Table 4.3: EDS analysis of master alloy particle from sample 3. for reference. 9 spots were chosen as a representation, as can be seen in figure 4.6.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]
1	4.63	37.61	33.03	8.99	15.23	7.53
2	2.46	39.89	37.47	8.59	10.98	0.62
3	3.24	38.64	32.71	10.11	14.82	0.48
6	46.99	26.15	0.68	8.69	16.74	0.75
7	43.56	22.88	0.19	10.89	21.72	0.76
8	50.30	29.36	0.60	7.48	11.53	0.73
11	32.61	19.51	18.42	9.72	19.11	0.63
12	30.98	20.06	33.63	5.99	8.74	0.59
13	28.62	17.30	19.07	11.55	22.93	0.53

4.2.2 Sample 4 - Temperature cycles T = 1550/1137 °C, holding time 3 hours

The day these SEM pictures were taken, the BSE-detector was out of order. This detector shows contrast between phases. Since no contrast between the phases could be seen in the middle and on the top of the sample, these pictures were not included. In section 4.3 a picture of this microstructure in these areas can be seen. Using the secondary electron detector, SiC particles could be detected in SEM as seen in figure 4.8.

Figure 4.7: EDS analysis of the left side of sample 4, showing the interactions between the graphite crucible and the alloy. The results are presented in table 4.4.

Table 4.4: EDS analysis of the interaction between the graphite crucible and the alloy on the left side of sample 4, from the spots shown in figure 4.7.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	33.70	20.58	35.55	6.45	3.06	0.66	-
2	54.84	34.37	2.35	5.82	1.60	1.01	SiFe
3	56.35	33.96	0.47	6.34	1.72	1.16	SiFe
4	54.26	0.06	0.16	0.24	44.74	0.54	SiC
5	56.77	0.07	0.17	0.07	42.38	0.55	SiC
6	62.36	0.08	0.22	4.04	32.47	0.83	SiC
7	57.26	34.83	1.22	4.15	1.79	0.76	SiFe
8	55.20	28.90	0.27	9.71	5.08	0.84	SiFe
9	34.63	22.10	5.00	11.43	26.04	0.80	SiFe
10	47.26	0.24	0.14	4.40	46.61	1.35	SiC
11	54.78	0.00	0.17	0.07	44.57	0.41	SiC
12	56.19	0.11	0.18	1.19	41.87	0.46	SiC
13	0.36	0.01	4.13	0.51	94.94	0.05	C
14	1.09	0.03	4.04	0.44	94.34	0.05	C
15	0.41	0.01	4.21	0.59	94.73	0.04	C
16	0.78	0.00	3.76	1.63	93.77	0.06	C
17	0.47	0.00	3.49	0.65	95.35	0.03	C
18	0.24	0.02	3.75	0.56	95.36	0.08	C

Figure 4.8: SEM picture of the left side of the sample. The graphite crucible can be seen on the left side of the picture (marked in green) and the Fe-Si-B alloy on the right side of the picture (marked in black). SiC particles can be seen in the alloy as big dark phases (marked in yellow).

The microstructure seen in figure 4.9 of the middle of sample 4, is similar to the microstructure found in sample 3 and the master alloy. The carbon content is ranging from 0.49 to 8.06 at% C (with one exception in spot no. 8 with 14.51 %at C), and the oxygen content is ranging from 2.62 to 6.23 %at O.

Figure 4.9: EDS analysis of the different phases in the middle of sample 4. The results are presented in table 4.5.

Table 4.5: EDS analysis of the different phases in the middle of sample 4, the spots can be seen in figure 4.9.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	45.52	42.62	1.36	5.60	3.41	1.50	SiFe
2	1.01	65.18	28.07	4.36	0.93	0.44	FeB
3	44.28	42.47	1.25	6.23	5.10	0.67	SiFe
4	42.50	37.66	4.47	5.72	8.06	1.58	SiFe
5	45.83	42.96	7.58	2.62	0.49	0.52	SiFe
6	31.34	30.91	31.02	3.06	2.57	1.10	-
7	35.98	32.85	24.46	3.19	2.72	0.81	-
8	17.85	15.56	45.73	5.57	14.51	0.78	-

Sample 4 was observed to have melted on the inside, but was uneven on the surface, which could indicate that the alloy did not melt on the outside. The results in table 4.6 show some spots that have very high oxygen and carbon content.

Figure 4.10: EDS analysis of the different phases at the top of sample 4. The results are presented in table 4.6.

Table 4.6: EDS analysis at the top of sample 4, the spots can be found in figure 4.10.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	3.52	11.91	13.37	63.13	7.70	0.38	Oxides?
2	27.67	3.78	16.57	31.52	20.03	0.43	Oxides/Carbides?
3	50.14	33.01	4.62	6.01	5.37	0.85	SiFe
4	44.46	33.27	7.70	6.96	7.11	0.50	SiFe
5	56.40	0.30	0.19	0.93	41.73	0.46	SiC
6	46.14	33.23	7.21	8.44	4.70	0.28	SiFe
7	6.10	4.29	6.48	3.27	79.73	0.14	C

4.2.3 Sample 5 - Temperature cycles $T = 1550/1137\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, holding time 3 hours

The microstructure observed in sample 5 at the top in figure 4.11, is similar to the microstructure found in the other samples. An indication of eutectic structure can be observed, in addition to the bigger white phase which is believed to be a primary phase. The carbon levels in the EDS analysis presented in table 4.7 are ranging from 0.02 to 2.15 at% C, which is quite low compared to the analyses

done of the other samples. The oxygen levels are ranging from 2.84 to 5.44 %at.

Figure 4.11: SEM picture of the top of sample 5.

Figure 4.12: EDS analysis of the top of sample 5, the analysis of the spots can be found in table 4.7

Table 4.7: EDS analysis at the top of sample 5, the spots can be found in figure 4.12.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	57.67	36.52	0.25	4.46	0.18	0.91	SiFe
2	57.76	36.22	0.25	4.59	0.32	0.85	SiFe
3	57.25	36.34	0.28	4.91	0.26	0.96	SiFe
4	28.12	20.20	47.98	2.84	0.31	0.55	SiFeB ₂
5	28.59	20.34	47.38	3.08	0.02	0.58	SiFeB ₂
6	27.41	19.94	49.23	3.00	0.03	0.40	SiFeB ₂
7	0.85	38.50	54.29	5.05	1.07	0.24	FeB
8	0.84	28.89	53.77	5.44	0.79	0.27	FeB
9	0.84	37.23	54.52	5.00	2.15	0.26	FeB

4.3 EPMA

EPMA was used to analyze the chemical composition of the different phases found in samples. This section will give an overview of the results, using average values of three data points in each phase to indicate the possible phase compo-

sition. In all analysis the phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ or SiFeB_2 were found. The two phases have a distinguished color difference and are mixed together in a lamellar structure which is believed to be eutectic. $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ has a brighter grey color than $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ and SiFeB_2 . A bigger white phase was identified in many of the samples, and had the composition FeB or $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$.

In this section an overview is presented of the phases found in the samples with mean values of the elements with standard deviation. A complete EPMA analysis can be found in the appendix.

4.3.1 Sample 3

4.3.1.1 Heat treated particle

In the EPMA analysis of the middle of the heat treated particle, small black particles with 9.06 at% of carbon were found.

Figure 4.13: Picture of phases found in the middle of the heat treated particles in sample 3.

Table 4.8: EPMA analysis from figure 4.13 of the middle of the heat treated particles from sample 3. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
10, 11, 12	37.75	7.73	44.08	0.90	9.06	0.48	Si ₄ FeB ₄ C
SD for 10, 11, 12	3.169	3.332	4.009	0.279	2.155	0.118	-
13, 14, 15	40.99	44.68	10.95	1.60	1.77	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 13, 14, 15	0.469	0.279	0.448	0.231	0.043	0.005	-
16, 17, 18	24.71	25.32	42.11	6.24	1.61	0.01	SiFeB ₂
SD for 16, 17, 18	2.013	1.299	5.829	2.520	0.057	0.008	-

At the surface of the heat treated particle, big black particles were observed as seen in figure 4.14. They had a composition of approximately 90 at% at B and 5

at% at C, which could be the phase B_4C . No carbon rich phases were observed at the surface as in the middle of the sample heat treated particle.

Figure 4.14: Picture of phases found at the surface of the heat treated particles in sample 3.

Table 4.9: EPMA analysis from figure 4.14 of the surface of the heat treated particles from sample 3. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1, 2, 3	1.23	0.30	91.10	1.08	5.14	1.14	B with 5 at% C
SD for 1, 2, 3	0.026	0.062	0.318	0.041	0.341	0.037	-
4, 5, 6	39.52	42.90	12.49	2.60	2.48	0.01	Si_4Fe_4B
SD for 4, 5, 6	0.519	1.079	0.264	0.941	0.390	0.009	-
7, 8, 9	21.13	22.73	51.40	2.72	2.02	0.02	$Si_2Fe_2B_5$
SD for 7, 8, 9	0.649	0.445	1.696	0.790	0.306	0.017	-

4.3.1.2 Master alloy as reference

In the analysis of the master alloy small black particles can be observed in figure 4.15. These had a carbon content of 7.31 at%, similar to the black particles found in the heat treated particle.

Figure 4.15: Picture of phases found in the master alloy used as reference to the heat treated particles in sample 3.

Table 4.10: EPMA analysis from figure 4.15 of the master alloy. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
19, 20, 21	39.24	15.84	34.97	1.83	7.31	0.81	Si ₄ FeB ₄ C
SD for 19, 20, 21	5.044	3.515	5.085	0.508	2.711	0.121	-
22	0.66	47.76	48.93	1.32	1.3	0.04	FeB
23, 24	40.87	44.47	10.32	2.22	2.13	0.01	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 23, 24	0.080	0.215	0.155	0.325	0.110	0.010	-
25, 26, 27	24.00	24.89	44.79	3.85	2.43	0.03	SiFeB ₂
SD for 25, 26, 27	1.158	0.572	3.305	1.482	0.156	0.008	-

4.3.2 The bottom of the samples 2, 4 and 5

The results from the EPMA analyses conducted of the bottom of samples 2, 4 and 5 is presented in this section. The phases Si₄Fe₄B and Si₂Fe₂B₅ were observed in all samples. At the interface between the graphite crucible and alloy, SiC particles were observed.

Figure 4.16: Picture of phases found at the bottom of sample 2.

Table 4.11: EPMA analysis from figure 4.16 of the bottom of sample 2. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1, 2, 3	40.96	44.55	11.73	0.93	1.76	0.08	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 1, 2, 3	0.096	0.249	0.286	0.029	0.009	0.017	-
4, 5, 6	20.06	21.73	54.92	1.45	1.69	0.15	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 4, 5, 6	0.595	0.555	1.489	0.323	0.120	0.014	-
7, 8, 9	8.88	0.42	86.62	0.53	1.71	1.83	B with 10 at% Si
SD for 7, 8, 9	0.320	0.182	1.236	0.266	0.248	0.231	-

Figure 4.17: Picture of the bottom of sample 2 showing traces of SiC-particles at the very bottom of the alloy.

Figure 4.18: Picture of the bottom of sample 4.

Table 4.12: EPMA analysis from figure 4.18 of the bottom of sample 4. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1, 2, 3	43.10	0.36	2.37	2.04	52.12	0.01	SiC
SD for 1, 2, 3	3.642	0.042	3.352	0.944	1.219	0.005	-
4, 5, 6	40.91	45.34	11.00	0.80	1.86	0.09	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 4, 5, 6	0.131	0.298	0.300	0.017	0.036	0.024	-
7, 8, 9	19.86	21.71	55.81	0.92	1.61	0.10	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 7, 8, 9	0.306	0.118	0.336	0.163	0.024	0.031	-
10, 11, 12	19.29	0.93	76.42	0.51	1.93	0.91	SiB ₄
SD for 10, 11, 12	0.708	0.578	1.249	0.123	0.033	0.082	-

Figure 4.19: Picture of the bottom of sample 5.

Table 4.13: EPMA analysis from figure 4.19 of the bottom of sample 5. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1, 2, 3	46.94	0.18	0.00	0.70	52.18	0.00	SiC
SD for 1, 2, 3	0.389	0.017	0.000	0.458	0.193	0.000	-
4, 5, 6	41.70	44.68	10.42	1.26	1.89	0.06	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 4, 5, 6	0.050	0.069	0.388	0.297	0.079	0.045	-
7, 8, 9	20.97	22.29	53.42	1.59	1.71	0.03	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 7, 8, 9	0.487	0.537	1.726	0.746	0.071	0.014	-
10, 11, 12	0.23	47.99	49.77	0.76	1.22	0.03	FeB
SD for 10, 11, 12	0.041	0.168	0.232	0.117	0.021	0.012	-

4.3.3 The middle of the samples 2, 4 and 5

In the middle of the samples, the same phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ were found as in the bottom of the samples. In sample 2 boron particles with 10 at% Si were found. Traces of small black boron particles can also be observed in sample 4 and 5, but the magnification of the picture was too low to analyze them.

Figure 4.20: Picture from the EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 2.

Table 4.14: EPMA analysis from figure 4.20 of the middle of sample 2. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
10, 11, 12	40.71	44.07	12.50	0.92	1.72	0.09	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 10, 11, 12	0.249	0.049	0.477	0.188	0.012	0.012	-
13, 14, 15	21.45	22.85	52.11	1.80	1.61	0.17	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 13, 14, 15	0.404	0.056	0.954	0.595	0.005	0.012	-
16, 17, 18	41.45	44.76	10.58	1.34	1.76	0.10	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 16, 17, 18	0.204	0.538	0.561	0.736	0.014	0.022	-
19, 20, 21	8.56	0.47	87.01	0.43	2.11	1.41	B with 10 at% Si
SD for 19, 20, 21	0.711	0.144	0.633	0.131	0.426	0.242	-

Figure 4.21: Picture from the EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 4.

Table 4.15: EPMA analysis from figure 4.21 of the middle of sample 4. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
13, 14, 15	27.93	45.50	23.89	1.01	1.65	0.02	$\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$
SD for 13, 14, 15	19.335	0.502	19.144	0.102	0.243	0.022	-
16, 17, 18	18.50	19.98	56.94	2.65	1.91	0.02	$\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$
SD for 16, 17, 18	2.233	2.067	3.029	1.325	0.387	0.009	-

Figure 4.22: Picture from the EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 5.

Table 4.16: EPMA analysis from figure 4.22 of the middle of sample 5. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
13, 14, 15	41.72	45.10	10.49	0.98	1.69	0.04	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 13, 14, 15	0.071	0.138	0.316	0.143	0.045	0.043	-
16, 17, 18	22.25	23.45	50.05	2.70	1.54	0.02	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 16, 17, 18	0.808	0.577	2.280	0.938	0.026	0.005	-
19, 20, 21	0.10	48.01	49.98	0.72	1.19	0.00	FeB
SD for 19, 20, 21	0.017	0.327	0.306	0.005	0.005	0.005	-

4.3.4 The top of the samples 2, 4 and 5

The results from the EPMA analyses conducted of the top of samples 2, 4 and 5 is presented in this section. The phases Si₄Fe₄B and Si₂Fe₂B₅ were observed in all samples. SiC particles were observed at the surface of the alloy in every sample. In sample 4 a darker phase is observed around the SiC particles, which probably is the phase B_{4+δ}C.

Figure 4.23: Picture from the EPMA analysis of the top of sample 2.

Table 4.17: EPMA analysis from figure 4.23 of the top of sample 2. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
22, 23, 24	40.86	44.06	12.12	1.18	1.75	0.04	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 22, 23, 24	0.127	0.019	0.122	0.244	0.005	0.026	-
25, 26, 27	20.78	22.08	52.75	2.69	1.61	0.09	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 25, 26, 27	0.128	0.290	1.141	1.287	0.014	0.017	-
28, 29, 30	41.19	44.92	10.74	1.35	1.74	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 28, 29, 30	0.152	0.200	0.691	0.635	0.043	0.012	-
31, 32, 33	46.83	0.75	0.00	2.77	49.63	0.02	SiC
SD for 31, 32, 33	0.259	0.051	0.000	1.174	0.949	0.005	-

Figure 4.24: Picture from the EPMA analysis of the top of sample 4.

Table 4.18: EPMA analysis from figure 4.24 of the top of sample 4. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
19, 20, 21	44.65	0.41	0.00	0.77	54.16	0.01	SiC
SD for 19, 20, 21	3.154	0.012	0.000	0.274	2.893	0.005	-
22, 23, 24	0.30	51.60	45.59	1.11	1.38	0.03	FeB
SD for 22, 23, 24	0.258	6.949	7.673	0.364	0.083	0.025	-
25, 26, 27	39.35	44.81	12.73	1.15	1.91	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 25, 26, 27	0.041	0.204	0.417	0.214	0.036	0.016	-
28, 29, 30	20.08	22.67	53.19	2.14	1.87	0.05	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 28, 29, 30	0.194	0.337	0.559	0.628	0.111	0.009	-
31, 32, 33	1.28	0.46	90.39	1.12	4.79	1.96	B with 5 at% C
SD for 31, 32, 33	0.226	0.069	1.089	0.651	0.340	0.116	-

Figure 4.25: Picture from the EPMA analysis of the top of sample 5.

Table 4.19: EPMA analysis from figure 4.25 of the top of sample 5. SD denotes standard deviation.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
22, 23, 24	46.52	0.26	0.00	0.36	52.87	0.00	SiC
SD for 22, 23, 24	2.129	0.034	0.000	0.059	2.187	0.000	-
25, 26, 27	41.12	44.39	12.01	0.75	1.65	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
SD for 25, 26, 27	0.114	0.198	0.195	0.114	0.029	0.009	-
28, 29, 30	19.69	21.74	56.22	0.86	1.46	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
SD for 28, 29, 30	0.128	0.069	0.166	0.033	0.005	0.005	-
31, 32, 33	0.18	47.73	50.20	0.71	1.17	0.01	FeB
SD for 31, 32, 33	0.074	0.373	0.309	0.077	0.014	0.019	-

Figure 4.26: CT scan of sample 1 in three different planes. (a) is taken in the XY-plane. (b) in the XZ-plane and (c) in the YZ-plane.

4.4 CT Scan

CT scans were taken of all the samples to investigate the porosity of the alloy. Half of the crucible with alloy from samples 1, 2, 4 and 5 were scanned. The whole crucible with alloy from sample 3 was scanned, since the crucible could not be cut as the particles were loose.

The grey phase that is the matrix is most likely a mix of the phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$, according to the EPMA results. The lighter grey phase shaped as needles, is most likely the phase FeB. The dark areas observed inside the alloy are pores. In all of the samples clusters of pores can be observed at the top of the alloy. In sample 4 and 5, cracks can be observed in all scans in the three different planes.

Figure 4.27: CT scan of sample 2 in three different planes. (a) is taken in the XY-plane. (b) in the XZ-plane and (c) in the YZ-plane.

Figure 4.28: CT scan of sample 3 in three different planes. (a) is taken in the XY-plane. (b) in the XZ-plane and (c) in the YZ-plane.

Figure 4.29: CT scan of sample 4 in three different planes. (a) is taken in the XY-plane. (b) in the XZ-plane and (c) in the YZ-plane.

Figure 4.30: CT scan of sample 5 in three different planes. (a) is taken in the XY-plane. (b) in the XZ-plane and (c) in the YZ-plane.

5. Discussion

5.1 Results from EPMA and EDS

Table 5.1 shows the phases predicted in Fe-Si-B alloy at room temperature by the phase diagrams, and gives an overview of the phases observed by Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1], Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10] and the author.

Table 5.1: Predicted phases by phase diagrams and the observed phases.

Expected phases	FeSi	FeB	SiB ₆	B ₄ C	-	-	-	-	-	-
Observed by Grorud [1]	-	FeB	SiB ₆	B ₄ C	B _{4+δ} C	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅	-	-	SiC
Observed by Sindland [10]	FeSi	-	-	B ₄ C	-	-	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅	-	-	SiC
Observed by the author	FeSi	FeB	-	-	B _{4+δ} C	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅	SiFeB ₂	SiB ₉	SiC

From the EPMA results the phases Si₄Fe₄B and Si₂Fe₂B₅ are found in all parts of the samples. The two phases are found in a lamellar structure, which indicates an eutectic structure [24]. Si₄Fe₄B has a light grey color, and Si₂Fe₂B₅ has a darker grey colors in the pictures presented in section 4.3. This is consistent with the results from Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1] and Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10]. However, Grorud discusses the possibility that the eutectic phase FeSi is falsely identified as Si₄Fe₄B. This could be an explanation to why Grorud did not identify the phase FeSi, but found large amounts of Si₄Fe₄B. In this study, FeSi was identified by XRD and EDS, but not with EPMA. With EPMA the phase Si₄Fe₄B was found in almost all samples. EDS and EPMA analyses have difficulties characterizing light elements, elements with atomic number below 11 [25],

and this matches Grorud's theory that boron might be falsely detected in this area. Boron rich phases around $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ are detected, which could be a source for noise in the analysis signal of $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$. The phase $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ is not found in the ternary phase diagram.

In many of the analysis pictures, a big white phase can be found. This has been identified to most likely be FeB or $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$, and is consistent with the results from Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1]. This phase appears to be a primary phase [24], and has most likely precipitated before crossing the eutectic isotherm.

SiC particles were found at the interface between the graphite crucible and the alloy, by Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1], Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10] and the author. Around the SiC particles as a layer, B_4C or $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found. The eutectic phase SiB_6 was identified by Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1] and Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10], but this phase was not identified in this study. However, the phase SiB_9 was found spread evenly through all parts of the samples as particles in clusters. Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1] also found boron rich phases with 10 at% Si [1], but Grorud assumed that it was the eutectic phase SiB_6 .

5.1.1 Analysis of the bottom of the sample

The phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ were identified in all samples at the bottom. The bigger white phase, FeB, was observed in sample 5. In sample 4 and 5 SiC-particles were observed on the interface between the alloy and the graphite crucible. In sample 2, SiC-particles were barely observed, due to a small magnification of the picture in figure 4.16, however in figure 4.17 SiC can be observed at the interface. In sample 2 and 4 black boron rich particles with silicon are observed, with phase composition SiB_9 and SiB_4 , however they could be the eutectic phase SiB_6 . Black particles can also be observed in sample 5, which is assumed to be the same boron rich phase SiB_6 , however they were not analyzed.

5.1.2 Analysis of the middle of the samples

The phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ were found in all samples. Boron rich particles with composition SiB_9 were analyzed in sample 2, and black particles are observed in sample 4 that could be the same particles. Also in sample 5, small black particles can be seen. The phase FeB , which is thought to be a primary phase, was identified in sample 5. In comparison, the microstructure in sample 2 looks more eutectic than the microstructure in sample 5. The different temperature programs that the samples has been through, could potentially be the source to the difference in microstructure.

5.1.3 Analysis of the top of the samples

Again were the phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ identified in all samples. SiC particles were also found near the surface of the alloy in all samples. In sample 4, the phase $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found as a layer around the SiC particles. The SiC particles are around $50 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter in sample 4 and 5, and in sample 2 the particles are around $5\text{-}10 \mu\text{m}$. Master alloy made by Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10] was used in experiment 2 and master alloy made by the author was used in experiments 4 and 5.

Since different master alloys were used in the experiments which gave different SiC particle sizes, it could indicate that the chemical composition of the master alloy is decisive. It would be interesting to see the difference in amount of carbon contamination in the two different master alloys, however carbon is a light element which cannot be characterized using ICP-MS [26].

5.1.4 5 days experiments vs. short experiments

Experiment 3 was the only short term experiment that was analyzed with EPMA. In both the heat treated particle from sample 3 and the master alloy (as reference), were the eutectic phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ found. In the middle of the

master alloy particle and the heat treated particle, small black particles with 7-9 at% C can be observed in the microstructure.

At the surface of the heat treated particle, boron rich particles with 5 at% carbon with size around 10 μm were found, which probably is the phase $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$. As seen in the phase diagram in figure 2.6, B_4C is precipitated at 1450°C in a carbon saturated Fe-Si-B-C system. There were not found any carbon rich phases around the surface of the heat treated particles, only $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$, $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$. In the middle of the same particle, the carbon rich phase with 7-9 at% carbon was found but not $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$. This could indicate that the carbon rich phases are supersaturating the area around them with carbon, and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ particles are precipitating at a lower temperature than 1450°C. As $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ is found on the surface of the heat treated particle after being exposed to one hour at 1250°C. $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ has a higher melting point than 1250°C, and could be creating a shell around the alloy particles that would prevent them from melting.

No SiC particles were found in sample 3, but was found in all the other experiments that lasted for 5 days. This could give an indication that the formation of SiC particles is time dependent. Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1] did similar experiments with the same materials, but for a shorter time with shorter intervals. In her results from EPMA, the SiC particles are around 20 μm and in the results presented here some of the SiC particles are around 50 μm . However, it is difficult to say if the results presented in Grorud's thesis are representative for the whole sample, and if they are completely comparable to the results presented in this study. It could therefore be interesting to investigate the formation of SiC particles in the alloy, and see if it is time dependent and to what degree.

5.2 Simulation of a Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage System

Experiments 2, 4 and 5 were done to simulate a LHTES, by running temperature cycles over and under the theoretical melting point, $T_m = 1157^\circ\text{C}$. All the samples

melted on the inside. The temperature gradient in the tube furnace was found to be 19.5 °C, which would effect the experiments. Experiment 2 was conducted with temperature cycles at $T_m \pm 20$ °C. Since the temperature gradient was almost 20 °C, this could indicate that the real temperatures in the alloy have been $T_{max} = 1157$ °C and $T_{min} = 1117$ °C. As previous studies [1] [10] have reported problems with melting the alloy over the eutectic melting point $T_m = 1157$ °C it might indicate that the alloy in experiment 2 did not melt during the temperature cycles. However, the sample was heated to 1550°C and held for one hour prior to the cycles. The alloy could have melted the first hour, and then been solid during the temperature cycles.

It was observed that experiment 4 had an uneven surface on the top, and it was believed at first that the alloy had not melted, as can be seen in figure 5.2. When the sample was cut, it could be observed that the alloy was in one piece and had melted on the inside.

Figure 5.1: Experiment 4 before temperature cycles

Figure 5.2: Experiment 4 after the temperature cycles

Figure 5.3: Sample 4 after mounting, indicating at the top of the sample where the analyses were taken to investigate the surface of the top.

Therefore, further investigations had to be done to see why sample 4 had not melted on the outside. The EDS-analyses showed indications of oxides and car-

bides on the surface. Oxides and carbides have a higher melting points than metals, which could explain why the surface of the alloy does not melt. From the EPMA-analyses silicon carbide were found on the surface, which is not wanted. Silicon carbide has a melting point of 2830°C[3], hence the particles would not melt in these experiments at these temperatures. As mentioned, the SiC-particles found by Grorud (Grorud 2018) [1] were slightly smaller than in this study. This could give an indication that the formation is time dependent, as Grorud's experiments were shorter. Also the SiC found by Sindland (Sindland 2018) [10] in her thesis, were smaller than what is found here. This should be investigated further.

The results from the wettability experiments showed that Fe-Si-B alloy has a low wettability on both graphite and alumina substrate, as the wetting angles were larger than 90°. In sample 2 and 4 the alloy fell out of the crucible during cutting, which can also indicate low wettability. If the liquid Fe-Si-B alloy is not wetting the graphite crucible very well, it implies that interactions are not very strong.

5.3 Investigation of the melting temperature

The second objective for this study was to investigate why the alloy sometimes does not melt above the theoretical melting temperature, which was calculated to be $T_m = 1157^\circ\text{C}$. Hence, wettability experiments were conducted with the master alloy in a wettability furnace to investigate at exactly what temperature the alloy would melt. The results showed that the alloy melted at 1230°C on graphite and at 1226°C on alumina. Jian Meng Jiao (NTNU) has also performed wettability experiments on the same alloy on graphite substrate, and reported that the alloy melted around 1220°C. These experiments indicate that the theoretical melting point is lower compared to the real melting point of the alloy. Further investigations to determine the alloys real melting point should be done, since the results are showing that the theoretical melting temperature deviates around

66°C from the real melting temperature.

Another explanation to why the alloy is not melting at the theoretical melting point, could be that the alloy is not at exactly eutectic composition. This could cause a variation in the the melting point of the alloy. The chemical composition of the master alloy is presented in table 3.3, and this deviates some from the wanted eutectic composition. This would affect the melting point of the alloy. Elevated levels of carbon rich phases were observed with EDS and EPMA in the master alloy. The EDS analysis also gave an indication that the master alloy contained 5.99-11.55 at% oxygen. The master alloy was not heat treated after the production, hence the impurities in the alloy are most likely to originate from the production. As mentioned in section 3.3, the crucible fell into the mould and the casted alloy during casting. This could be the source of the impurities found in the master alloy. In the 5 days experiment, no carbon rich phases were found in the middle of the alloy. This could either indicate that the carbon is migrating to the surface of the alloy, either at the interface with the crucible or at the top of the alloy, or that the master alloy's chemical composition is inhomogeneous. As the master alloy was not stirred during production, this could be a possible explanation.

A leaching process with acid could be done to the master alloy prior to the experiments in order to rule out any possible oxide layer on the surface which could interfere with the results.

5.4 Results from CT Scan

The CT scans were presented in section 4.4, and was taken of all of the samples. The scans showed clustered cavities at the top of the alloy in the samples, which was a repeating result in all of the scans. In the scan conducted on sample 3, a porous structure can be seen in some parts of the heat treated alloy which did not melt. In the scans of sample 4 and 5 distinctive cracks can be observed

through the whole sample. These cracks could have been introduced during the phase transformation between liquid and solid state.

6. Conclusion

In all the samples the phases $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$ and $\text{Si}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{B}_5$ were observed, and they are believed to be eutectic phases. The big white phase was observed in many of the samples, and was identified as FeB or $\text{Si}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{B}$. Along the interface between the alloy and the carbon crucible, SiC was found. This is consistent with the same analyses from previous studies [1] [10]. In this study, the phase $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found in some of the samples, in sample 3 this phase was present at the surface of the particles that did not melt. In sample 4, $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found around the SiC particles at the top of the sample.

The alloy in sample 3 did not melt at $1250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The analyses show carbon rich particles in both the heat treated particle as well as in the master alloy. This carbon rich phase was not found in any of the other samples. At the surface of the unmelted alloy, the phase $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found and not the carbon rich phase. $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ is precipitating at $1450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a carbon saturated Fe-Si-B alloy, however the carbon rich phases found have carbon levels higher than the saturation limit. $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ could have precipitated due to a supersaturation of carbon. This phase is found around the surface of the alloy in experiment 3 and could have created some sort of protective shell around the alloy, preventing the alloy from melting. The carbon rich phase found in some samples could indicate that the master alloy is inhomogeneous. The impurities could originate from the crucible that fell into the mould during casting. Another explanation to why these carbon rich phases are not found in the other samples, could be that the carbon possibly is

migrating during the temperature cycles to the surface of the alloy. Since SiC was found around the surface of the alloy, both at the interface and the top of the sample.

In the 5 days experiments SiC was found on the interface between the graphite crucible and the alloy, and on the top of the sample. From sample 4 the analyses show the phase $B_{4+\delta}C$ precipitated around the SiC particles. However, silicon carbide has a high thermal conductivity, k , in the range of 0,5-1,2 W/cm*K [4]. Which is in the same range as Fe-Si-B alloy at 27°C; 0,852 W/cm*K [1]. Pure boron has a thermal conductivity of $k = 0,27$ W/cm*K [3], which is more than 3 times lower than the thermal conductivity of the alloy. A high thermal conductivity in the particles around the surface of the alloy would mean a low thermal gradient, and could ensure that the heat from the surroundings reach the middle of the alloy and vice versa.

This could indicate that the unwanted silicon carbide particles are not an obstacle for this system's application as LHTES. As further work, it would be interesting to measure the amount of silicon carbide accumulating in the samples over time, and to investigate if the formation is time dependent or not.

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A. Appendix

A.1 EPMA analyses

A.1.1 Sample 2

Figure A.1: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 2

Table A.1: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 2.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	40.86	44.28	12.12	0.94	1.75	0.06	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
2	40.93	44.88	11.45	0.89	1.75	0.10	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
3	41.09	44.48	11.61	0.96	1.77	0.09	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
4	19.98	21.63	55.62	1.04	1.60	0.14	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
5	19.38	21.10	56.29	1.48	1.61	0.14	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
6	20.83	22.45	52.85	1.83	1.86	0.17	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
7	8.70	0.29	87.43	0.35	1.55	1.67	B (90%B with 10%Si)
8	8.61	0.30	87.55	0.34	1.52	1.67	B (90%B with 10%Si)
9	9.33	0.68	84.87	0.91	2.06	2.16	B (90%B with 10%Si)

Figure A.2: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 2.

Table A.2: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 2.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	40.44	44.06	13.00	0.70	1.70	0.11	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
2	40.64	44.01	12.65	0.90	1.72	0.08	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
3	41.04	44.13	11.86	1.16	1.73	0.09	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
4	21.88	22.83	50.87	2.64	1.61	0.17	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
5	20.91	22.80	53.19	1.31	1.61	0.18	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
6	21.56	22.93	52.27	1.46	1.62	0.15	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
7	41.34	44.15	10.25	2.38	1.77	0.11	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
8	41.74	45.46	10.12	0.79	1.77	0.12	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
9	41.28	44.68	11.37	0.85	1.74	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
10	9.41	0.60	86.12	0.38	2.32	1.16	B (90%B with 10%Si)
11	7.67	0.54	87.34	0.61	2.50	1.34	B (90%B with 10%Si)
12	8.60	0.27	87.56	0.30	1.52	1.74	B (90%B with 10%Si)

Figure A.3: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 2.

Table A.3: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 2.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	40.99	44.07	12.12	1.03	1.74	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
2	40.69	44.07	11.97	1.52	1.75	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
3	40.91	44.03	12.27	0.98	1.75	0.06	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
4	20.73	22.06	53.52	1.98	1.60	0.11	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
5	20.96	21.73	51.14	4.50	1.60	0.08	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
6	20.66	22.44	53.60	1.60	1.63	0.07	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
7	41.40	44.71	9.77	2.25	1.80	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
8	41.14	44.86	11.31	0.94	1.70	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
9	41.04	45.19	11.15	0.87	1.72	0.04	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
10	46.75	0.73	0.00	2.07	50.43	0.02	SiC
11	46.56	0.70	0.00	4.42	48.30	0.02	SiC
12	47.18	0.82	0.00	1.81	50.17	0.03	SiC

A.1.2 Sample 3

Figure A.4: EPMA analysis in the middle of a particle of the master alloy as a reference to the heat treated particles in sample 3.

Table A.4: EPMA analysis in the middle of the master alloy.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	32.38	20.81	41.08	1.37	3.62	0.74	Si ₃ Fe ₂ 4B ₄
2	44.37	13.44	28.63	2.54	10.05	0.98	Si ₄ FeB ₃ C
3	40.96	13.27	35.20	1.59	8.27	0.71	Si ₄ FeB ₃ C
4	0.66	47.76	48.93	1.32	1.30	0.04	FeB
5	40.79	44.25	10.16	2.54	2.24	0.02	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	40.95	44.68	10.47	1.89	2.02	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	23.15	24.79	47.18	2.52	2.34	0.02	SiFeB ₂
8	25.64	25.63	40.12	5.92	2.65	0.04	SiFeB ₂
9	23.22	24.24	47.08	3.12	2.30	0.03	SiFeB ₂

Figure A.5: EPMA analysis on the surface of the heat treated particle in sample 3.

Table A.5: EPMA analysis on the surface of the heat treated particle from sample 3.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	1.21	0.23	91.09	1.03	5.30	1.14	B
2	1.22	0.29	90.71	1.13	5.46	1.19	B
3	1.27	0.38	91.49	1.09	4.67	1.10	B
4	39.82	43.86	12.28	1.78	2.24	0.02	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
5	38.79	41.39	12.86	3.92	3.03	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	39.95	43.44	12.32	2.11	2.17	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	20.25	22.23	53.75	1.89	1.88	0.01	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
8	21.33	22.64	49.81	3.78	2.44	0.00	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
9	21.80	23.31	50.64	2.48	1.73	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅

Figure A.6: EPMA analysis of the middle of the heat treated particle in sample 3.

Table A.6: EPMA analysis in the middle of the heat treated particle from sample 3.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	41.04	11.93	39.00	0.67	6.70	0.65	Si ₄ FeB ₄
2	33.47	7.48	48.80	1.29	8.57	0.39	Si ₄ FeB ₄ C
3	38.74	3.78	44.43	0.73	11.91	0.41	Si ₄ B ₄ C
4	41.64	44.56	10.33	1.68	1.79	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
5	40.76	45.07	11.17	1.29	1.71	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	40.56	44.42	11.36	1.84	1.81	0.01	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	21.86	23.49	50.35	2.68	1.61	0.01	SiFeB ₂
8	26.15	26.10	38.01	8.06	1.68	0.00	SiFeB ₂
9	26.11	26.37	37.96	7.99	1.54	0.02	SiFeB ₂

A.1.3 Sample 4

Figure A.7: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 4.

Table A.7: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 4.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	46.72	0.40	0.00	1.42	51.45	0.01	SiC
2	44.47	0.37	0.00	1.32	53.83	0.00	SiC
3	38.12	0.30	7.11	3.37	51.08	0.01	SiC
4	40.91	45.74	10.58	0.79	1.91	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
5	41.07	45.02	11.19	0.82	1.83	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	40.75	45.27	11.24	0.78	1.84	0.12	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	19.56	21.59	55.92	1.15	1.64	0.14	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
8	19.74	21.67	56.15	0.80	1.58	0.07	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
9	20.28	21.87	55.35	0.81	1.61	0.08	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
10	18.29	0.51	77.94	0.35	1.97	0.95	SiB ₄
11	19.83	1.75	74.88	0.65	1.89	0.99	SiB ₄
12	19.75	0.54	76.45	0.53	1.93	0.80	SiB ₄

Figure A.8: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 4.

Table A.8: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 4.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	0.59	46.21	50.96	0.92	1.31	0.01	FeB
2	41.57	45.16	10.23	1.15	1.84	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
3	41.64	45.13	10.47	0.95	1.81	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
4	19.30	21.01	56.93	1.09	1.64	0.03	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
5	20.74	21.84	53.23	2.53	1.64	0.03	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
6	15.45	17.10	60.65	4.33	2.46	0.01	SiFeB ₄

Figure A.9: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 4.

Table A.9: EPMA analysis on the top of sample 4.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	40.23	0.40	0.00	1.16	58.20	0.00	SiC
2	47.38	0.43	0.00	0.60	51.59	0.01	SiC
3	46.34	0.41	0.00	0.56	52.68	0.01	SiC
4	0.66	61.43	34.74	1.61	1.50	0.06	Fe ₂ B
5	0.15	46.62	51.15	0.76	1.31	0.02	FeB
6	0.08	46.76	50.88	0.95	1.34	0.00	FeB
7	39.30	45.03	12.27	1.39	1.96	0.05	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
8	39.34	44.87	12.64	1.18	1.89	0.07	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
9	39.40	44.54	13.28	0.87	1.88	0.03	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
10	19.81	22.45	53.91	1.77	2.03	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
11	20.17	22.42	52.55	3.02	1.78	0.06	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
12	20.26	23.15	53.10	1.62	1.81	0.06	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
13	1.32	0.37	90.91	0.59	4.76	2.05	B
14	0.99	0.46	91.38	0.74	4.39	2.04	B
15	1.54	0.54	88.87	2.04	5.22	1.80	B

A.1.4 Sample 5

Figure A.10: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 5.

Table A.10: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 5.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	46.44	0.16	0.00	1.35	52.05	0.00	SiC
2	46.99	0.20	0.00	0.35	52.45	0.00	SiC
3	47.39	0.17	0.00	0.41	52.03	0.00	SiC
4	41.66	44.68	9.93	1.68	1.93	0.12	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
5	41.77	44.76	10.44	1.05	1.96	0.02	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	41.67	44.59	10.88	1.05	1.78	0.03	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	20.87	21.99	54.06	1.38	1.66	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
8	21.61	23.04	51.06	2.59	1.66	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
9	20.43	21.83	55.14	0.80	1.81	0.01	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
10	0.18	48.09	49.55	0.92	1.25	0.01	FeB
11	0.22	48.12	49.67	0.73	1.22	0.03	FeB
12	0.28	47.75	50.09	0.64	1.20	0.04	FeB

Figure A.11: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 5.

Table A.11: EPMA analysis in the middle of sample 5.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	41.66	45.29	10.04	1.17	1.75	0.10	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
2	41.68	45.02	10.71	0.93	1.66	0.00	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
3	41.82	44.98	10.71	0.83	1.65	0.02	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
4	23.15	24.18	47.69	3.39	1.58	0.01	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
5	22.41	23.39	49.32	3.33	1.53	0.02	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
6	21.19	22.77	53.13	1.37	1.52	0.02	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
7	0.12	47.62	50.35	0.72	1.19	0.00	FeB
8	0.08	48.42	49.60	0.72	1.18	0.00	FeB
9	0.11	48.00	49.98	0.71	1.19	0.01	FeB

Figure A.12: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 5.

Table A.12: EPMA analysis on the top of sample 5.

Spot No.	Si [at%]	Fe [at%]	B [at%]	O [at%]	C [at%]	Al [at%]	Possible compound
1	43.51	0.21	0.00	0.32	55.96	0.00	SiC
2	47.96	0.29	0.00	0.31	51.44	0.00	SiC
3	48.09	0.27	0.00	0.44	51.21	0.00	SiC
4	41.06	44.29	12.28	0.69	1.62	0.06	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
5	41.28	44.22	11.82	0.91	1.69	0.08	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
6	41.02	44.67	11.94	0.65	1.64	0.08	Si ₄ Fe ₄ B
7	19.67	21.71	56.26	0.88	1.46	0.03	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
8	19.86	21.84	56.00	0.81	1.46	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
9	19.55	21.68	56.40	0.88	1.45	0.04	Si ₂ Fe ₂ B ₅
10	0.19	48.01	50.00	0.60	1.16	0.04	FeB
11	0.27	47.20	50.64	0.74	1.16	0.00	FeB
12	0.09	47.97	49.97	0.78	1.19	0.00	FeB